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ALGORITHM FOR SOLVING TRANSIENT RESPONSE IN RC ELECTRONIC CIRCUITS USING COMPUTER ANALYSIS

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Introduction. *The article discusses a methodological approach to the study of transients in RC electronic circuits using computing tools. Special attention is paid to the development of an algorithm that provides a solution to the problem of analyzing the transient response through computer modeling. The proposed algorithm is based on a mathematical description of the dynamics of an RC circuit and takes into account both analytical and numerical methods for solving differential equations. The results of theoretical calculations were compared with computer analysis data, which made it possible to identify the degree of overlap and clarify the scope of the proposed methodology. The practical significance of the work lies in the possibility of using the algorithm to automate engineering calculations, optimize the parameters of electronic circuits and increase the effectiveness of the educational process in the study of transients in electrical systems.*

Keywords. *RC circuit; transient process; electronic circuits; computer analysis; solution algorithm; numerical methods; mathematical modeling; automation of calculations.*

Figure 1. Electrical diagram with n capacitors

The solution of the problem of analyzing the transient process in electrical circuits is relevant in the design and creation of radio engineering systems [1].

The mathematical model of the problem. For computer analysis of transients in electrical circuits, a mathematical model of this problem must first be compiled. To do this, enter the following designations for the parameters of the elements that make up the chain: i_k – current, u_k – voltage, C_k – the capacitance of the capacitor and R_k – resistance of the resistive element k - th section of the chain; t – time. The chain consists of n parallel connected sections.

Using the laws of Ohm and Kirchhoff [2], we can write the following formulas:

$$i_k = C_k \frac{du_k}{dt}, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

$$i(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n i_k(t); \quad (2)$$

$$u_1 = u_k + R_k i_k, k = 2, 3, \dots, n. \quad (3)$$

In all cases, the currents i_k and voltages U_k are functions of time t .

After simple transformations from formulas (1)-(3), the following system of first-order differential equations can be obtained:

$$\frac{du_k}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_1} \left[i(t) + \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{u_k - u_1}{R_k} \right], \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{du_k}{dt} = \frac{u_1 - u_k}{C_k R_k}, k = 2, 3, \dots, n.$$

The system of equations (4) consists of n equations with respect to the desired values of stresses in the sections of the circuit: $u_k(t), k = 1, 2, \dots, n$. The current values can be determined from formulas (2) and (3). From the second circuit switching law [3], it follows that at the initial moment of connecting the current source, at $t=0$, the following initial conditions can be written:

$$u_k(0) = 0, k = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

So, based on the results of mathematical modeling of the problem of analyzing the transient process in an electric RC circuit, we can formulate the Cauchy problem for the system of differential equations (4) and (5): *find a solution to the system of equations (4) in $0 \leq t \leq T$, satisfying the initial conditions (5)*. Here T is the time of the transient analysis.

About the method of solving the problem. The system of differential equations (4) is linear. The existence and uniqueness of the solution of the Cauchy problem (4) – (5) are considered in sufficient detail in the mathematical literature [4]. In this case, all the conditions of the existence and uniqueness theorem of the solution for such a system of equations are met.

An analytical solution to problem (4) – (5) is possible, but for a problem where the number of unknown functions is large enough, the solution will be obtained in the form of very cumbersome formulas. This creates certain difficulties during practical application in the design of electronic devices. In this regard, it is advisable to have a computer program (or algorithm) for analyzing such processes in electrical circuits. Therefore, in this paper, we consider an algorithm for the numerical solution of the problem posed here.

For convenience in further calculations, it is advisable to switch to dimensionless quantities. The following parameters are accepted as characteristic values [5]: R -resistance, U -voltage, T -time. Variables are being replaced:

$$\begin{cases} i = \frac{U}{R} \cdot f(t), i_k = \frac{U}{R} \cdot y_k(t), \\ u_k = U \cdot x_k(t); f = \frac{t}{T}. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

In this case, the function $f(t)$ it is considered known, and the function $y_k(t)$ and $x_k(t)$ unknown; in further entries, a dash over a dimensionless time value t will be omitted.

The use of variable substitution (6) allows us to obtain the following formulas in dimensionless quantities:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{\alpha_1} \left[f(t) + \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{x_k - x_1}{\beta_k} \right], \\ \frac{dx_k}{dt} = \frac{x_k - x_1}{\alpha_k}, k = 2, 3, \dots, n, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $\alpha_1 = \frac{RC_1}{T}$, $\alpha_k = \frac{R_k C_k}{T}$, $\beta_k = \frac{R_k}{R}$ – dimensionless constants [6]. (In the theory of electrical circuits [1] $R_k C_k$ it is considered constant in time and has the dimension of time).

From the initial conditions (5), it follows that

$$t = 0, x_k(0) = 0, k = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (8)$$

The solution of problem (7)-(8) is sought in the interval $0 \leq t \leq 1$, where t – dimensionless time.

For the numerical solution of the problem (7)-(8), the following formulas are considered

$$\begin{cases} x_{1i} = x_{1_{i-1}} + \frac{\delta}{\alpha_1} \left[f(t_{i-1}) + \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{x_{ki-1} - x_{1_{i-1}}}{\beta_k} \right], \\ x_{ki} = x_{ki-1} + \frac{\delta}{\alpha_k} (x_{ki-1} - x_{1_{i-1}}), k = 2, 3, \dots, n. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Here δ – the step of partitioning the interval $\{1;0\}$; $m = \frac{1}{\delta}$ – number of time steps t ; $x_{ki} = x_k(t_i)$. In the future, to simplify the entries, the notation is introduced: $x_{ki} = x_k$; $x_{ki-1} = z_k$.

The algorithm for solving the problem consists of the following steps:

- 1) Entering data for the values of constant parameters.
- 2) Determining the initial values of the desired functions ($x_k = 0; k = 1, 2, \dots, n.$) for $i = 0$.
- 3) Assigning values x_k parameters z_k , T.e. $z_k = x_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$.
- 4) Cycle to calculate new values of the functions x_k by formulas (9).
- 5) Output of function values x_k for the current value [7] i (or t).
- 6) Go to the calculation of the following values of the desired functions: $i = i + 1$ and checking the condition $i \leq m$ – the end of the calculation.

Conclusions. The conducted research has shown that the application of an algorithmic approach to the analysis of transients in RC electronic circuits provides higher accuracy and efficiency of computational procedures compared with traditional manual calculation methods. The developed algorithm, based on a combination of an analytical description of the dynamic properties of an RC circuit and computer modeling methods, makes it possible to effectively solve the problems of analyzing the system response under various input influences. A comparison of the results of theoretical calculations with the data of a numerical experiment confirmed the correctness of the proposed methodology and demonstrated its practical applicability. Thus, the use of computer

analysis of transient processes opens up new opportunities for optimizing the parameters of electronic circuits, improving engineering practice and improving the quality of the educational process in the field of electrical engineering and telecommunications.

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